

INTERVAL-VALUED FUZZY ALMOST BI-IDEALS OF NEAR-RINGS

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ABSTRACT. In this paper, we introduce the concept of interval valued fuzzy almost bi-ideals of near-rings. Which is a generalized concept of fuzzy almost bi-ideals of near-rings. We also characterize some properties and provide examples of interval-valued fuzzy almost bi-ideals of near-rings.

1. INTRODUCTION

In 1965, the definition of fuzzy subsets was introduced by Zadeh [28]. In 1971, Rosenfeld [18] extended the concept of fuzzy set theory to group theory and defined fuzzy group. Kuroki [12] studied various kinds of fuzzy ideals in semigroups and characterized them. Interesting research on fuzzy semigroups can be found in [11]. In 2011, Chon [3] also characterized the fuzzy bi-ideal generated by fuzzy subsets in semigroups. In 1980, Grosek and Satko [6] defined and studied the notion of left (respectively, right, two-sided) almost ideals of semigroups. Moreover, they characterized when a semigroup S contains no proper left (respectively, right, two-sided) almost ideals. In 1981, Bogdanovic [2] introduced the notion of almost bi-ideals in semigroups. Fuzzy ideals of rings were exhibited by W. Liu [15] and it has been studied by several authors [7, 12, 17]. The notions of fuzzy subnear-ring, fuzzy ideals of near-rings were ushered by Salah Abou-Zaid [1]. The concept of bi-ideals was applied to near-rings in [19]. Manikantan [16] introduced the notion of fuzzy bi-ideals of near-rings and discussed some of its properties. The notion of fuzzy almost bi-ideals of near-rings [27]. In this paper, we first give some properties of interval valued fuzzy almost bi-ideals of near-rings and introduce the notion of interval valued fuzzy almost bi-ideals by using the concepts of fuzzy almost bi-ideals and fuzzy ideals of near-rings. Moreover, we explore some characterization interval valued fuzzy almost bi-ideals of near-rings.

2. PRELIMINARIES

Definition 2.1. A non-empty set N with two binary operations $+$ and \cdot is called a near-ring if

(1) $(N, +)$ is a group,

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(2) (N, \cdot) is a semigroup,

(3) $x \cdot (y + z) = x \cdot y + x \cdot z$, for all $x, y, z \in N$.

We use word 'near-ring' to mean 'left near-ring'. We denote xy instead of $x \cdot y$. Note that $x0 = 0$ and $x(-y) = -xy$ but in general $0x \neq 0$ for some $x \in N$.

Definition 2.2. An ideal I of a near-ring N is a subset of N such that

(4) $(I, +)$ is a normal subgroup of $(N, +)$,

(5) $NI \subseteq I$,

(6) $((x + i)y - xy) \in I$ for any $i \in I$ and $x, y \in N$

Note that I is a left ideal of N if I satisfies (4) and (5), and I is a right ideal of N if I satisfies (4) and (6).

Definition 2.3. A two sided N -subgroup of a near-ring N is a subset H of N such that

(i) $(H, +)$ is a subgroup of $(N, +)$,

(ii) $NH \subset H$,

(iii) $HN \subset H$.

If H satisfies (i) and (ii) then it is called a left N -subgroup of N . If H satisfies (i) and (iii) then it is called a right N -subgroup of N .

Definition 2.4. Let N be a near-ring. Given two subsets A and B of N , the product $AB = \{ab | a \in A, b \in B\}$ Also we define another operation ' $*$ ' on the class of subsets of N given by $A * B = \{a(a' + b) - aa' | a, a' \in A, b \in B\}$.

Definition 2.5. A subgroup B of $(N, +)$ is said to be a bi-ideal of N if $BNB \cap BN * B \subseteq B$.

Definition 2.6. Let X be any non-empty set. A mapping $\lambda : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is called a fuzzy subset of X .

Definition 2.7. Let μ and λ be any two fuzzy subsets of N . Then $\mu \cap \lambda, \mu \cup \lambda, \mu + \lambda, \mu\lambda$, $\mu \subseteq \lambda$ and $\mu * \lambda$ are fuzzy subsets of N defined by:

$$(\mu \cap \lambda)(x) = \min\{\mu(x), \lambda(x)\}.$$

$$(\mu \cup \lambda)(x) = \max\{\mu(x), \lambda(x)\}.$$

$$\mu \subseteq \lambda \text{ if } \mu(x) \leq \lambda(x)$$

$$(\mu + \lambda)(x) = \begin{cases} \sup_{x=y+z} \{\min\{\mu(y), \lambda(z)\}\} & \text{if } x \text{ is expressible as } x = y+z, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

$$(\mu\lambda)(x) = \begin{cases} \sup_{x=yz} \{\min\{\mu(y), \lambda(z)\}\} & \text{if } x \text{ is expressible as } x = yz, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

for all $x \in N$. Let λ be a fuzzy subset of N . The support of λ is define by support $\lambda := \{x \in N | \lambda(x) \neq 0\}$.

Definition 2.8. Let A be a non-empty subset of N . The characteristic mapping of A is a fuzzy subset of N defined by

$$C_A(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \in A, \\ 0 & \text{if } x \notin A. \end{cases}$$

Definition 2.9. Let s be any element in N . The characteristic mapping of s is a fuzzy subset of N defined by

$$C_s(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x = s, \\ 0 & \text{if } x \notin s. \end{cases}$$

Definition 2.10. A fuzzy subset λ of a near-ring N is called a fuzzy N -subgroup of N if

- (1) λ is a fuzzy subgroup of $(N, +)$
- (2) $\lambda(xy) \geq \lambda(y)$
- (3) $\lambda(xy) \geq \lambda(x)$, for all $x, y \in N$.

A fuzzy subset with (1) and (2) is called a fuzzy left N -subgroup of N , whereas a fuzzy subset with (1) and (3) is called a fuzzy right R -subgroup of N .

$$(\lambda * \mu)(x) = \begin{cases} \sup_{x=a(b+c)-ab} \{\min\{\lambda(a), \mu(c)\}\} & \text{if } x \text{ is expressible as } x = a(b+c)-ab, \\ \bar{0} & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Definition 2.11. A fuzzy subset λ of a near-ring N is called a fuzzy subnear-ring of N if $\forall x, y \in N$,

- (i) $\lambda(x - y) \geq \min\{\lambda(x), \lambda(y)\}$
- (ii) $\lambda(xy) \geq \min\{\lambda(x), \lambda(y)\}$

If a fuzzy subset λ of a near-ring N satisfies the property (i), then letting $x = y$, we have $\lambda(0) \geq \lambda(x) \forall x \in N$.

Definition 2.12. Let λ be a non-empty fuzzy subset of N . λ is a fuzzy ideal of N , if for all $x, y, i \in N$ and

- (1) $\lambda(x - y) \geq \min\{\lambda(x), \lambda(y)\}$
- (2) $\lambda(x) = \lambda(y + x - y)$
- (3) $\lambda(xy) \geq \lambda(x)$
- (4) $(\lambda(x(y + i) - xy) \geq \lambda(i))$ for any $x, y, i \in N$.

If λ satisfies (1), (2) and (3), then it is called a fuzzy right ideal of N . If λ satisfies (1), (2) and (4), then it is called a fuzzy left ideal of N . If λ is both fuzzy right as well as fuzzy left ideal of N , then λ is called a fuzzy ideal of N .

Definition 2.13. A fuzzy subgroup λ of N is called a fuzzy bi-ideal of N if for all $x \in N$, $((\lambda \circ N \circ \lambda) \cap (\lambda \circ N) * \lambda)(x) \leq \lambda(x) \rightarrow (1)$

If N is zero symmetric, then (1) reduces $(\lambda \circ N \circ \lambda)(x) \subseteq \lambda(x)$.

Definition 2.14. [10] An interval number \bar{a} on $[0,1]$ is a closed subinterval of $[0,1]$, that is, $\bar{a} = [a^-, a^+]$ such that $0 \leq a^- \leq a^+ \leq 1$ where a^- and a^+ are the lower and upper end limits of \bar{a} respectively. The set of all closed subintervals of $[0, 1]$ is denoted by $D[0, 1]$.

We also identify the interval $[a, a]$ by the number $a \in [0, 1]$. For any interval numbers $\bar{a}_i = [a_i^-, a_i^+], \bar{b}_i = [b_i^-, b_i^+] \in D[0, 1], i \in I$, we define

$$\begin{aligned} \max^i\{\bar{a}_i, \bar{b}_i\} &= [\max^i\{a_i^-, b_i^-\}, \max^i\{a_i^+, b_i^+\}], \\ \min^i\{\bar{a}_i, \bar{b}_i\} &= [\min^i\{a_i^-, b_i^-\}, \min^i\{a_i^+, b_i^+\}], \\ \inf^i \bar{a}_i &= \left[\bigcap_{i \in I} a_i^-, \bigcap_{i \in I} a_i^+ \right], \sup^i \bar{a}_i = \left[\bigcup_{i \in I} a_i^-, \bigcup_{i \in I} a_i^+ \right] \end{aligned}$$

In this notation $\bar{0} = [0, 0]$ and $\bar{1} = [1, 1]$. For any interval numbers $\bar{a} = [a^-, a^+]$ and $\bar{b} = [b^-, b^+]$ on $[0, 1]$, define

- (1) $\bar{a} \leq \bar{b}$ if and only if $a^- \leq b^-$ and $a^+ \leq b^+$.
- (2) $\bar{a} = \bar{b}$ if and only if $a^- = b^-$ and $a^+ = b^+$.

- (3) $\bar{a} < \bar{b}$ if and only if $\bar{a} \leq \bar{b}$ and $\bar{a} \neq \bar{b}$
 (4) $k\bar{a} = [ka^-, ka^+]$, whenever $0 \leq k \leq 1$.

Definition 2.15. [10] Let X be any set. A mapping $\bar{A} : X \rightarrow D[0, 1]$ is called an interval-valued fuzzy subset (briefly, i-v fuzzy subset) of X where $D[0, 1]$ denotes the family of all closed subintervals of $[0, 1]$ and $\bar{A}(x) = [A^-(x), A^+(x)]$ for all $x \in X$, where A^- and A^+ are fuzzy subsets of X such that $A^-(x) \leq A^+(x)$ for all $x \in X$.

Note that $\bar{A}(x)$ is an interval (a closed subset of $[0, 1]$) and not a number from the interval $[0, 1]$ as in the case of fuzzy subset.

Definition 2.16. [10] A mapping $min^i : D[0, 1] \times D[0, 1] \rightarrow D[0, 1]$ defined by $min^i(\bar{a}, \bar{b}) = [min\{a^-, b^-\}, min\{a^+, b^+\}]$ for all $\bar{a}, \bar{b} \in D[0, 1]$ is called an interval min-norm.

Definition 2.17. [10] A mapping $max^i : D[0, 1] \times D[0, 1] \rightarrow D[0, 1]$ defined by $max^i(\bar{a}, \bar{b}) = [max\{a^-, b^-\}, max\{a^+, b^+\}]$ for all $\bar{a}, \bar{b} \in D[0, 1]$ is called an interval max-norm.

Let min^i and max^i be the interval min-norm and max-norm on $D[0, 1]$ respectively. Then the following are true.

1. $min^i\{\bar{a}, \bar{a}\} = \bar{a}$ and $max^i\{\bar{a}, \bar{a}\} = \bar{a}$ for all $\bar{a} \in D[0, 1]$.
2. $min^i\{\bar{a}, \bar{b}\} = min^i\{\bar{b}, \bar{a}\}$ and $max^i\{\bar{a}, \bar{b}\} = max^i\{\bar{b}, \bar{a}\}$ for all $\bar{a}, \bar{b} \in D[0, 1]$.
3. If $\bar{a} \geq \bar{b} \in D[0, 1]$, then $min^i\{\bar{a}, \bar{c}\} \geq min^i\{\bar{b}, \bar{c}\}$ and $max^i\{\bar{a}, \bar{c}\} \geq max^i\{\bar{b}, \bar{c}\}$ for all $\bar{c} \in D[0, 1]$.

Definition 2.18. [10] Let \bar{A} be an i-v fuzzy subset of a set X and $[t_1, t_2] \in D[0, 1]$. Then the set $\bar{U}(\bar{A} : [t_1, t_2]) = \{x \in X | \bar{A}(x) \geq [t_1, t_2]\}$ is called the upper level set of \bar{A} .

Note that

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{U}(\bar{A} : [t_1, t_2]) &= \{x \in X | [A^-(x), A^+(x)] \geq [t_1, t_2]\} \\ &= \{x \in X | A^-(x) \geq t_1\} \cap \{x \in X | A^+(x) \geq t_2\} \\ &= (U(A^- : t_1)) \cap (U(A^+ : t_2)). \end{aligned}$$

Definition 2.19. [1] If $\bar{\lambda}$ and $\bar{\mu}$ are i-v fuzzy subsets of a near-ring N . Then

$\bar{\lambda} \cap \bar{\mu}, \bar{\lambda} \cup \bar{\mu}, \bar{\lambda} + \bar{\mu}, \bar{\lambda}\bar{\mu}$ and $\bar{\lambda} * \bar{\mu}$ are i-v fuzzy subsets of N defined by,

$$\begin{aligned} (\bar{\lambda} \cap \bar{\mu})(x) &= \min^i\{\bar{\lambda}(x), \bar{\mu}(x)\} \\ (\bar{\lambda} \cup \bar{\mu})(x) &= \max^i\{\bar{\lambda}(x), \bar{\mu}(x)\} \end{aligned}$$

$$(\bar{\lambda} + \bar{\mu})(x) = \begin{cases} \sup_{x=y+z}^i \{\min^i\{\bar{\lambda}(y), \bar{\mu}(z)\}\} & \text{if } x \text{ is expressible as } x = y+z, \\ \bar{0} & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

$$(\bar{\lambda}\bar{\mu})(x) = \begin{cases} \sup_{x=yz}^i \{\min^i\{\bar{\lambda}(y), \bar{\mu}(z)\}\} & \text{if } x \text{ is expressible as } x = yz, \\ \bar{0} & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

$$(\bar{\lambda} * \bar{\mu})(x) = \begin{cases} \sup_{x=a(b+c)-ab}^i \{\min^i\{\bar{\lambda}(a), \bar{\mu}(c)\}\} & \text{if } x \text{ is expressible as } x = a(b+c)-ab, \\ \bar{0} & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

3. INTERVAL-VALUED FUZZY ALMOST BI-IDEALS (IVFABIS)

In this section, we define IVFABIs in NR and give some relationship between ABIs and IVFABIs of NR.

Definition 3.1. Let $\bar{\mu}$ be an Interval-valued fuzzy subset of N such that $\bar{\mu} \neq \bar{0}$. $\bar{\mu}$ is called an IVFABI of N if $\forall n \in N, (\bar{\mu}C_n\bar{\mu}) \cap (\bar{\mu}C_n * \bar{\mu}) \cap \bar{\mu} \neq \bar{0}$.

Theorem 3.1. Let $\bar{\mu}$ be a IVFABI of N and $\bar{\nu}$ be an interval-valued fuzzy subset of $N \ni \bar{\mu} \subseteq \bar{\nu}$. Then $\bar{\nu}$ is a IVFABI of N .

Proof. Let $\bar{\mu}$ is an IVFABI of N and $\bar{\nu}$ is an interval-valued fuzzy subset of N such that $\bar{\mu} \subseteq \bar{\nu}$. Then $\forall n \in N, (\bar{\mu}C_n\bar{\mu}) \cap (\bar{\mu}C_n * \bar{\mu}) \cap \bar{\mu} \subseteq (\bar{\mu}C_n\bar{\nu}) \cap (\bar{\nu}C_n\bar{\nu} * \bar{\mu}) \cap \bar{\nu}$ and $(\bar{\mu}C_n\bar{\mu} \cap \bar{\mu}C_n * \bar{\mu}) \cap \bar{\mu} \neq 0$. This implies $(\bar{\nu}C_n\bar{\nu} \cap \bar{\nu}C_n * \bar{\nu}) \cap \bar{\nu} \neq 0, \forall n \in N. \therefore \bar{\nu}$ is an IVFABI. \square

Corollary 3.2. Let $\bar{\mu}$ and $\bar{\nu}$ is an IVFABI of N . Then $\bar{\mu} \cup \bar{\nu}$ is an IVFABI of N .

Proof. Since $\bar{\mu} \subseteq \bar{\mu} \cup \bar{\nu}$ by Theorem 3.1, $\bar{\mu} \cup \bar{\nu}$ is an IVFABI of N . \square

Example 3.2. Consider Z_5 under the usual addition. Let $\bar{\mu} : Z_5 \rightarrow D[0, 1]$ be defined by $\bar{\mu}(\bar{0}) = 0, \bar{\mu}(\bar{1}) = 0.5, \bar{\mu}(\bar{2}) = 0, \bar{\mu}(\bar{3}) = 0.1, \bar{\mu}(\bar{4}) = 0.1$ and $\bar{\nu} : Z_5 \rightarrow D[0, 1]$ be defined by $\bar{\nu}(\bar{0}) = 0, \bar{\nu}(\bar{1}) = 0.2, \bar{\nu}(\bar{3}) = 0$ and $\bar{\nu}(\bar{4}) = 0.2$. We have $\bar{\mu}$ and $\bar{\nu}$ are IVFABIs of Z_5 but $\bar{\mu} \cap \bar{\nu}$ is not an IVFABI of Z_5 .

Theorem 3.3. Let $B(\neq \emptyset) \subseteq N$ of N . Then B is an ABI of N iff \bar{C}_B is an IVFABI of N .

Proof. Let B is an ABI of N . Then $BnB \cap Bn * B \cap B \neq 0 \forall n \in N$. Thus there $\exists x \in BnB, x \in Bn * B$ and $x \in B$. So $(\bar{C}_B\bar{C}_n\bar{C}_B)(x) = \bar{1}, (\bar{C}_B\bar{C}_n * \bar{C}_B)(x) = \bar{1}$ and $\bar{C}_B(x) = 1$. Hence $(\bar{C}_B\bar{C}_n\bar{C}_B) \cap (\bar{C}_B\bar{C}_n * \bar{C}_B) \cap \bar{C}_B \neq \bar{0}$ for all $n \in N. \therefore \bar{C}_B$ is an IVFABI of N .

Conversely, assume that \bar{C}_B is an IVFABI of N . Let $n \in N$. Then $((\bar{C}_B\bar{C}_n\bar{C}_B) \cap (\bar{C}_B\bar{C}_n * \bar{C}_B)) \cap \bar{C}_B \neq \bar{0}$. Then $\exists x \in N \ni [((\bar{C}_B\bar{C}_n\bar{C}_B) \cap (\bar{C}_B\bar{C}_n * \bar{C}_B)) \cap \bar{C}_B](x) \neq \bar{0}$. Hence $x \in BnB \cap (Bn * B) \cap B$. So, $BnB \cap (Bn * B) \cap B \neq 0 \forall n \in N$. Consequently, B is an ABI of N . \square

Theorem 3.4. Let $\bar{\mu}$ be an interval valued fuzzy subset of N . Then $\bar{\mu}$ is an IVFABI of N iff $\text{supp } \mu$ is an ABI of N .

Proof. Let $\bar{\mu}$ be an IVFABI of N . Let $n \in N$. Then $\bar{\mu}(C_n\bar{\mu}) \cap (\bar{\mu}C_n * \bar{\mu}) \cap \bar{\mu} \neq \bar{0}$. Hence for each $n \in N$, there $\exists x \in N \ni [(\bar{\mu}C_n\bar{\mu}) \cap (\bar{\mu}C_n * \bar{\mu}) \cap \bar{\mu}](x) \neq 0$. So there $\exists y_1, y_2, y_3 \in N$ such that $x = y_1ny_2$ and $x = y_1n(y_2n + y_3) - (y_1n)(y_2n), \bar{\mu}(x) \neq \bar{0}, \bar{\mu}(y_1) \neq \bar{0}, \bar{\mu}(y_2) \neq 0$ and $\bar{\mu}(y_3) \neq \bar{0}$ That is $x, y_1, y_2, y_3 \in \text{supp } \bar{\mu}$. Thus $(C_{\text{supp } \bar{\mu}}C_nC_{\text{supp } \bar{\mu}})(x) \neq \bar{0}$. Therefore $((C_{\text{supp } \bar{\mu}}C_nC_{\text{supp } \bar{\mu}}) \cap (C_{\text{supp } \bar{\mu}}C_n * C_{\text{supp } \bar{\mu}})) \cap C_{\text{supp } \bar{\mu}} \neq \bar{0}$. Hence $C_{\text{supp } \bar{\mu}}$ be a IVFABI of N . By Theorem 3.3, $\text{supp } \mu$ be an ABI of N .

Conversely, assume that $\text{supp } \mu$ be an ABI of N . By Theorem 3.3, $C_{\text{supp } \bar{\mu}}$ be a IVFABI of N . Then $(C_{\text{supp } \bar{\mu}}C_nC_{\text{supp } \bar{\mu}}) \cap (C_{\text{supp } \bar{\mu}}C_n * C_{\text{supp } \bar{\mu}}) \cap C_{\text{supp } \bar{\mu}} \neq \bar{0}$ for all $n \in N$. Then there $\exists x \in N \ni [(C_{\text{supp } \bar{\mu}}C_nC_{\text{supp } \bar{\mu}}) \cap (C_{\text{supp } \bar{\mu}}C_n * C_{\text{supp } \bar{\mu}}) \cap C_{\text{supp } \bar{\mu}}](x) \neq \bar{0}$. Hence $\left((C_{\text{supp } \bar{\mu}}C_nC_{\text{supp } \bar{\mu}}) \cap (C_{\text{supp } \bar{\mu}}C_n * C_{\text{supp } \bar{\mu}}) \cap C_{\text{supp } \bar{\mu}} \right) (x) \neq \bar{0}$ and $C_{\text{supp } \bar{\mu}}(x) \neq \bar{0}$.

Then there $\exists y_1, y_2 \in N$ such that $x = y_1ny_2, \bar{\mu}(x) \neq \bar{0}, \bar{\mu}(y_1) \neq \bar{0}$ and $\bar{\mu}(y_2) \neq \bar{0}$. This means $(\bar{\mu}C_n\bar{\mu}) \cap (\bar{\mu}C_n * \bar{\mu}) \cap \bar{\mu} \neq \bar{0}. \therefore \bar{\mu}$ is an IVFABI of N . \square

4. MINIMAL INTERVAL VALUED FUZZY ALMOST BI-IDEALS (MIVFABIS)

In this section, we define MAIVFBIs in NR and study relationship between support and MAFBIs of NRs.

Definition 4.1. A IVFABI $\bar{\mu}$ is called minimal if for each IVFABI $\bar{\nu}$ of N such that $\bar{\mu} \subseteq \bar{\nu}$, we have $\text{supp } \bar{\nu} = \text{supp } \bar{\mu}$.

Theorem 4.1. Let $B(\neq \emptyset) \subseteq N$. Then B is a MABI of N iff \bar{C}_B is a MIVFABI of N .

Proof. Let B is a MABI of N . By Theorem 3.3, \overline{C}_B is a IVFABI of N . Let \overline{g} be a IVFABI of $N \ni \overline{g} \subseteq \overline{C}_B$. Then $\text{supp}\overline{g} \subseteq \text{supp}\overline{C}_B = B$. Since $\overline{g} \subseteq \overline{C}_{\text{supp}\overline{g}}$, we have $(\overline{g}\overline{C}_B\overline{g}) \cap (\overline{g}\overline{C}_B * \overline{g}) \cap \overline{g} \subseteq (\overline{C}_{\text{supp}\overline{g}}\overline{C}_B\overline{C}_{\text{supp}\overline{g}}) \cap (\overline{C}_{\text{supp}\overline{g}}\overline{C}_B * \overline{C}_{\text{supp}\overline{g}}) \cap \overline{C}_{\text{supp}\overline{g}}$. Thus $\overline{C}_{\text{supp}\overline{g}}$ is an IVFABI of N . By Theorem 3.3, $\text{supp}\overline{g}$ is an ABI of N . Since B is minimal, $\text{supp}\overline{g} = B = \text{supp}\overline{C}_B$. $\therefore C_B$ is minimal.

Conversely, assume that \overline{C}_B is an MIVFABI of N . Let B' be an ABI of $N \ni B' \subseteq B$. Then $\overline{C}_{B'}$ is an IVFABI of N such that $C_{B'} \subseteq C_B$. Hence $B' = \text{supp}C_{B'} = \text{supp}C_B = B$. $\therefore B$ is minimal. \square

Corollary 4.2. N has no proper ABI of N iff \forall IVFABI $\overline{\mu}$ of N , $\text{supp}\overline{\mu} = N$.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this study the notion of interval valued fuzzy almost bi-ideals and minimal interval valued fuzzy almost bi-ideals of near-rings have been presented and some properties of these ideals are derived.

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